

Deliverable 1.5

Strategic Alignment and Contribution to the EOSC Partnership

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	30/04/2025, M35
Actual Submission Date	28/05/2025
Work Package	WP1 Project Coordination and Strategic Alignment
Task	1.3
Type	Report
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – 27

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable outlines the strategic alignment activities that have taken place during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, and the project contributions to the EOSC partnership at the time of the project life cycle, and the forecasts of EOSC contributions in future. Moreover, it summarises the lessons learned on the course of the project to give recommendations to the future projects.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

DELIVERY SLIP

Contribution	Name	Partner/Activity	ORCID ID
Lead authors	Elisa Halonen	CSC	
	Tommi Suominen	CSC	0000-0002-4382-7425
Contributors	Mark van de Sanden	SURF	0000-0002-2718-8918
	Anna-Lena Flügel	DKRZ	0000-0001-8218-9609
	Fanny Adloff	DKRZ	0000-0003-1519-754X
	Joonas Nikkanen	CSC	0000-0002-5036-6444
	Joonas Kesäniemi	CSC	0000-0002-3770-0006
	Anssi Kainulainen	CSC	0009-0006-4244-1500
	Mike Bennett	DataCite	0000-0002-4795-7817
	Heinrich Widmann	DKRZ	0000-0001-9871-2687
	Themis Zamani	GRNET	0000-0003-1148-1738
	Hannes Thiemann	DKRZ	0000-0002-2329-8511
	Wim Hugo	KNAW-DANS	0000-0002-0255-5101
	Clifford Tatum	SURF	0000-0002-2212-3197
	Morane Gruenpeter	INRIA	0000-0002-9777-5560
	Sara Bozzi	Trust-IT	0009-0000-3922-3728
	Sven Bingert	GWDG	0000-0001-9547-1582
Willem Elbers	CLARIN	0000-0002-0191-9102	
Reviewer(s)	Daan Broeder	CLARIN ERIC	0000-0002-8446-3410
	Roksana Wilk	ACC Cyfronet AGH	0009-0006-5321-1006
Editorial review	Elisa Halonen	CSC	
	Anu Märkälä	CSC	0009-0009-1462-749X

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author/Editor/Reviewer
v.0.1	24/03/2025	First outline of the document	Elisa Halonen
v.0.2	09/04/2025	Contributions from partners	All partners
v.0.3	12/04/2025	Peer review	Daan Broeder, Roksana Wilk
v.0.4	28/04/2025	Address peer review comments	All partners
v.1.0	28/05/2025	Final version	Elisa Halonen Anu Märkälä

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
HE	Horizon Europe
EOSC-A	EOSC Association, that is one of the governing entities of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
FAIR	A principle that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
EOSC EU Node	Reference Gateway of European Commission with a purpose to streamline scientific data access (wrt. EOSC Node, a national node for an interoperable network of services, a building block of EOSC federation).
WP	Work Package
TBT	Technical Bridging Team
MSCR	The Metadata Schema Crosswalk Registry allows registered users and communities to search, create, register and version schemas and crosswalks with PIDs.
DTR	The EOSC Data Type Registry allows the registration of many different data types.
PIDGraph	The EOSC PID Graph offers a service to explore the DOIs and metadata from the DataCite data file through an API and regular data dumps.
PIDMR	The PID Meta Resolver offers a uniform interface that allows PIDs from different systems to be resolved and can simplify various processes.
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit, a service being developed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project to assist with EOSC PID Policy compliance assessment.
RAiD	The RAiD service provides persistent, unique and resolvable information for research projects.
RSAC	The Research Software APIs and Connectors ensure the long-term preservation of research software in different disciplines
SWHM	The EOSC Software Heritage Mirror is a copy of the Software Heritage universal source code archive, operated in agreement with, but independently from the Software Heritage organization.
RDGraph	The EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph) delivers advanced discovery tools across EOSC resources and communities.
PID	Persistent Identifier
ENES	The European Network for Earth System Modelling
RDA	Research Data Alliance
MVE	Minimum Viable EOSC

Table of Contents

- 1. Introduction..... 1
- 2. EOSC Partnership 3
 - 2.1 EOSC Association Task Forces 2024-2025..... 3
 - 2.1.1. Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force 3
 - 2.1.2 FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force..... 4
 - 2.1.3 PID Task Force..... 4
 - 2.2 EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups 5
 - 2.2.1 OA1: Persistent Identifiers 5
 - 2.2.2 OA2: Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability..... 6
 - 2.2.3 OA7: Research Software..... 6
 - 2.3 EOSC Federation 6
 - 2.3.1 EOSC Interoperability Framework..... 7
 - 2.3.2 Evolving EOSC-Core implementation..... 7
 - 2.4 HE INFRAEOSC Coordination 8
 - 2.4.1 HE INFRAEOSC Coordination Meetings 8
 - 2.4.2 HE Technology Working Group 10
 - 2.4.3 HE Communication and Engagement Working Group..... 10
 - 2.4.4 HE Impact Working Group 11
 - 2.4.5 EOSC Macro Roadmap 11
- 3. Horizon Europe Projects (mostly INFRAEOSC) 11
 - 3.1 FAIR-IMPACT 12
 - 3.2 RAISE 13
 - 3.3 GraspOS..... 14
 - 3.4 Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions (RDA TIGER) 14
 - 3.5 EOSC Beyond..... 15
 - 3.5.1 EOSC Beyond workshops 15
 - 3.5.2 EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox..... 15
 - 3.6 OSTrails 16
 - 3.7 EVERSE 16
 - 3.8 Biodiversity Digital Twin (BioDT)..... 17
- 4. Strategic communities 18
 - 4.1 ENES Climate Modelling Community 18
 - 4.2 CLARIN Community 20
 - 4.3 EuroCRIS..... 20

4.4	EUDAT.....	21
4.5	Research Data Alliance (RDA).....	22
4.5.1	RDA Working Groups	22
4.6	SWITCH	23
4.7	GWDG Lol PIDinst proposal.....	24
5	Lessons learned	24
6	Conclusions	26
	Appendix A: FAIRCORE4EOSC representation in RDA plenaries and other events	28

List of Tables

Table 1: Targeted actors for Strategic Alignment Activities	2
Table 2: Projects with whom FAIRCORE4EOSC collaborated	12

Executive Summary

The FAIRCORE4EOSC is a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) project, funded from Horizon Europe programme, that is tasked to develop nine new EOSC-Core services to support a FAIR EOSC as well as to enhance interoperability and discoverability of an increased amount of research outputs. The services are developed by leveraging existing technologies and services. Furthermore, the project has ensured the user centricity of the component development by identifying case studies, implemented by partners coming from different scientific communities. The case studies are early adopters of the services within these communities.

The main purpose of this report is to present the strategic alignment activities carried out during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. By strategic alignment we mean being informed of and actively contributing to the EOSC development at large and engaging the project in a diverse set of activities with relevant stakeholders to exploit synergies and maximise the impact of FAIRCORE4EOSC in the view of the EOSC mission and vision.

Strategic alignment can take different forms, and the level of engagement in alignment activities can vary depending on resources allocated for such activities, and the maturity of the project outputs. The FAIRCORE4EOSC approach was to share knowledge on different developments, raise awareness of project outputs and targeted dissemination. Sharing knowledge was crucial to find synergies so that the work does not take place in silos. It prevented misalignment of efforts between actors and duplication of work. Raising awareness for project outputs helped to ensure that the developed services matched the needs of users through engaging identified actors in requirement elicitation and validation of developed features. Both broad and targeted dissemination helped in finding interested users and increasing adoption of the developed services.

The alignment activities of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project have been classified into groups by target actor type: EOSC partnership, INFRAEOSC projects, strategic communities, and other stakeholders. The alignment activities are outlined in this report alongside the challenges that the project has overcome to improve the sustainability of the project contributions in the EOSC partnership.

The report also outlines the contribution to the EOSC partnership that the project has built during the project and that continues to produce impact after the project as well as the lessons that the project has learned by conducting the alignment activities during the project.

1. Introduction

FAIRCORE4EOSC¹, funded from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, is a research and innovation action (RIA) project contributing to the Co-programmed European Partnership on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices (European Union, 2021) across the European Research Area (ERA)². As such it contributes to several actions of the ERA policy agenda. EOSC is also recognised in the European strategy for data as the data space for science, research and innovation.

FAIRCORE4EOSC has developed nine new EOSC-Core components (language from the project grant agreement, EOSC-Core services or just services from now on) in order to support a FAIR EOSC and to enhance interoperability and discoverability of research outputs. Development activities of the services (WP2-6) were carried out by utilising existing services and technologies, as far as possible. To ensure that development of services was driven by the needs of users, the project has identified five user-centric case studies (WP7). The case studies also acted as early adopters of the services in the communities they represent.

At the time of the proposal writing, FAIRCORE4EOSC planned strategic alignment activities mainly with the EOSC Partnership to onboard the services developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC in the EOSC-Core (at that time intended to be in the form of the EOSC Portal developed by the EOSC Future project). This expectation totally changed during the course of the project as the EOSC Portal was dismissed and the concept of EOSC Nodes was introduced³.

This re-conceptualisation of the EOSC-Core has prevented the project to onboard the services into the EOSC Core because by the end of the project none of the EOSC nodes except the EOSC EU Node is operational. FAIRCORE4EOSC started a dialogue with the European Commission to understand if there were intentions to onboard the FAIRCORE4EOSC services in the EOSC EU Node but a negative answer was received (please also note that at the end of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, it is still not possible to onboard services in the EOSC EU Node). Many of the strategic alignment activities were therefore dedicated to closely following those EOSC developments to understand the potential sustainability and adoption of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services.

Even though the context for the services has changed considerably, the primary FAIRCORE4EOSC outputs to support a FAIR EOSC have just been released to the public (March 2025). All These services concretely contribute to improving the discoverability and interoperability of a continuously increasing amount of research outputs, even with a looser EOSC coupling. They are agnostic in discipline or geography and general in nature - and will surely gain further adoption both within and beyond EOSC. The plans for further service adoption are described in deliverable D7.3 “Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities”.

During the proposal writing process four strategic actors with whom the project would need to collaborate were identified to ensure the impact of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project outputs to the European research landscape:

¹ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101057264>

² [European research area - European Commission](#)

³ Due to the EOSC Federation and Node concept, introduced by the EOSC procurement, the concepts of the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE), the EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and Federated Data as described in the FAIR lady report (European Union, 2020) from the Sustainability Working Group and used in the FAIRCORE4EOSC proposal and project’s contract with the European Commission, became unclear and are still subject to change. The proposal and the Description of Action part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Grant Agreement acknowledged that FAIRCORE4EOSC largely relies on the results of EOSC Future.

EOSC partnership, INFRAEOSC projects, strategic communities, and other stakeholders. These actors are categorised below according to the type of foreseen collaboration at the start of the project.

Types of targeted actors: EOSC partnership, INFRAEOSC projects, strategic communities, and other stakeholders.

Table 1: Targeted actors for Strategic Alignment Activities

<p>Known knowns⁴</p> <p><i>Collaborations with entities known at project design time, such as: euroCRIS, RDA, EOSC Future, EOSC Association, EOSC Task Forces</i></p>	<p>Known Unknowns</p> <p>⁵<i>Especially the winner of the parallel call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-05 was put as a requirement, without knowing who it will be (FAIR-IMPACT).</i></p> <p><i>Later projects from calls that were not published at project design phase (though a fair expectation could be made that such will appear): EOSC Beyond, GraspOS, OSTrails, EVERSE</i></p>
<p>Unknown Knowns⁶</p> <p>BioDT (we knew of them, but didn't see the connection to our project).</p> <p><i>Some parallel calls that we didn't see so relevant for collaboration, until they were granted and we saw synergies, such as RAISE.</i></p>	<p>Unknowns Unknowns⁷</p> <p>SWITCH (unexpected development collaboration)</p> <p>RDATiger (unexpected opportunity to get support to establish an RDA Working Group)</p> <p><i>Closure of EOSC Platform (though a dependency to it was pre-identified as a risk)</i></p>

The planned collaboration (known knowns) is practical, as it can be resourced and planned on the side of both parties. For collaborating and aligning work with organisations you do not know at the stage in which you plan and resource your work, is challenging. Also, reciprocity may be an issue, if the other party does not have the resources for the needed collaboration. Starting a collaboration that is topically complementary to your work but that you were not prepared for (unknown unknown), might make sense content-wise, but one that might for example come at an inconvenient time. For FAIRCORE4EOSC being a RIA, we consider our engagement

⁴ During the writing of the proposal, besides the project partners themselves, we have named organisations such as euroCRIS and RDA as expert communities to engage with.

⁵ The call texts often call for collaboration with projects that will be awarded from specific parallel calls. In the proposal you can name calls, the winners of which you would like to collaborate with (you can plan, but you cannot promise, as you do not know who the projects will be awarded to). One might know of a consortium planning to submit a proposal for a given call, but you cannot really plan on a collaboration, because that consortium might not win the call.

⁶ These are elements that we do not realize we know. They are typically overlooked, or dismissed as irrelevant. We will dismiss this item in the quadrant as irrelevant for our strategic alignment topic.

⁷ There are always things we did not think or know about. With broadcast oriented communications, speaking at events to an open public, we do not know if someone will approach you, and come tell you about an initiative you have never heard of in e.g. Japan - that is working on solving the same problem. These kinds of situations can be great opportunities for a project, but possibly also disasters. In a good scenario two groups can pool their resources, in a way where both benefit from reaching an even better end solution.

to have been strategic, timely and very plentiful. We have tried to give space to both planned and unforeseen collaboration opportunities to maximise the impact of our service development work.

This report introduces the strategic alignment activities carried out during the project life-cycle of the FAIRCORE4EOSC and outlines the contributions of the project to the EOSC partnership in present and in future. Chapters two, three and four outline the strategic alignment activities carried out within the EOSC Partnership, with other projects and communities in the landscape. Chapter five will outline the lessons learned from these alignment activities and chapter six concludes the report.

2. EOSC Partnership

During the project life-cycle, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project has striven for alignment with different working groups, meetings and other activities within the EOSC Partnership to share knowledge and information, seek alignment with EOSC developments and the EOSC Federation, and to contribute to different policies and roadmaps. The EOSC Focus project, supporting the EOSC Partnership in achieving its mission, has been an important contact point for FAIRCORE4EOSC because, guided by the EOSC Association (EOSC-A), it has organised and facilitated many coordination activities for the EOSC community.

The collaboration with the EOSC partnership was also an additional evaluation sub-criterion for the call⁸, so this was also emphasised in the project design phase. The importance of alignment and coordination has increased especially due to the changes in EOSC implementation, which have also caused the project a fair share of challenges.

FAIRCORE4EOSC partners have represented the project in three different EOSC-A Task Forces (EOSC-A TF), three EOSC-A Opportunity Area Experts Groups (EOSC-A OA) and actively participated in three Horizon Europe Working Groups (WG).

2.1 EOSC Association Task Forces 2024-2025

The Task Forces are part of the “brain pool” of the EOSC-A. Experts from the FAIRCORE4EOSC consortium partners were active in ten of the EOSC-A TFs that completed their two-year mandate in December 2023⁹. A call for new TFs was opened in spring 2024, and several experts from FAIRCORE4EOSC were selected to the TFs for Technical and Semantic Interoperability¹⁰; FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects¹¹; and PIDs¹². The work of FAIRCORE4EOSC has been presented at TF meetings on several occasions, to inform the expert community of the work carried out in FAIRCORE4EOSC.

2.1.1 Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force

The task force consists of three subgroups on i) Technical Interoperability, ii) Semantic Interoperability and iii) Authentication and Authentication Infrastructure. Six representatives from partners of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (DKRZ, SURF, AGH-AGH/UST, OpenAIRE, CSC, CERN) are contributing to the Technical and Semantic Interoperability subgroups. The Technical and Semantic subgroups started with a landscaping exercise describing the current status of the technical and semantic interoperability in the EOSC Federation, including a gap analysis. This exercise provided good background information for the development work in

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2021-eosc-01-03>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/eosc-a-task-forces-2021-2023/>

¹⁰ EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force - EOSC Association

¹¹ FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force - EOSC Association

¹² PID Policy and Implementation - EOSC Association

FAIRCORE4EOSC. In addition, the project could present its work in TF meetings explaining how the services developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC will improve the discoverability and interoperability of research outputs.

2.1.2 FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force

The FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF includes two experts active within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (DKRZ, CERN). The TF focuses on advancing the practical implementation of FAIR principles, metrics, and Digital Object management, aiming to enhance data-level interoperability and reusability across the EOSC ecosystem. The involvement in the TF has provided FAIRCORE4EOSC with a crucial channel for bidirectional knowledge exchange with other TF members (e.g. insights on practical FAIR implementation in different communities) and collection of requirements for the development work in the project.

2.1.3 PID Task Force

The PID task force convened for 2 years and organised a session in the Madrid EOSC Symposium in 2023. The topical Opportunity Area 1 (OA1) follow-up started in the autumn of 2023 after the Madrid meeting, addressed a very similar topic, focussing on PIDs, and has carried on the work of the PID TF. A difference is that the TF also engaged people from outside the EOSC projects, while the OA1 is contained to EOSC project staff only.

Themis Zamani from GRNET (and also representing FAIRCORE4EOSC) was selected as co-chair of the TF. Also, DataCite was active in the TF. The PID TF carried out an inventory of current PID services and an inventory of projects and activities around PIDs. The primary focus of the TF was on information exchange. The FAIRCORE4EOSC members communicated the project's efforts on many occasions and used the forum to discuss project related development ideas our representatives also learned of other organisations and project's ongoing and past works.

A beta version of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit has been in operation since M18. CAT has actively engaged the PID TF and the community on multiple occasions to gather feedback on the assessment model, the proposed content for evaluating the EOSC PID Policy, and the beta version of the tool itself. Feedback and suggestions for improvement are presented in a public document¹³. These activities included contributions to the EOSC PID Policy Task Force, collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects, and close coordination with FAIR-IMPACT. A key highlight was the in-depth discussion on the EOSC PID Policy assessment, best practices supporting its implementation, and the use of the CAT (Capability Assessment Tool), which took place during the previous EOSC Winter School in Thessaloniki and the second one in Seville. Additionally, proposals for updates to the PID Policy were accepted by the EOSC PID Policy Task Force.

At the Winter School of 2024 the discussions of the Task Force were focused on the emerging PID (RAI, RAiD, PIDInst, MA DMPs, SWHID) and on the PID integration systems (PID Graph, PID Meta Resolver). Most of them are part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)¹⁴ was presented as a crucial emerging PID that enables project-level identification and integration within the broader EOSC ecosystem. It was Integrated into discussions on Metadata Interoperability, and of course it was demonstrated in many use cases. As a result, RAiD is one of the key PIDs in supporting FAIR Digital Objects¹⁵ by linking all components of a research project. SWHID (Software HashIdentifier)¹⁶ was highlighted as a key component in the evolving PID ecosystem, particularly for enabling the FAIR treatment of software. The **PID Meta Resolver** and the **PID Graph** were presented as foundational components of the **PID infrastructure** being advanced by

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8403957>

¹⁴ <https://raid.org/>

¹⁵ <https://fairdo.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.swhid.org/>

FAIRCORE4EOSC, aimed at improving interoperability, discoverability, and automation across the research ecosystem.

2.2 EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups

Several experts who are active in FAIRCORE4EOSC are also active members in the OAs for Persistent Identifiers OA¹⁷ (DataCite, KNAW-DANS, GREENT, GDWG, CSC), Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability OA¹⁸ (CSC, AGH/AGH-UST), and Research Software OA¹⁹ (Fondation Inria, CERN, FIZ).

In the INFRAEOSC projects coordination meeting of June 2023, the projects suggested to have a forum where also technical experts could discuss the topical synergies between the HE projects, not just the coordinators having a forum for high level talks. Consequently, the EOSC Focus project carried out a landscape study of what topics the ongoing EOSC projects address, by carrying out interviews of experts in the projects, including FAIRCORE4EOSC. This took place around the summer of 2023. Based on this work, six thematic groups were formed. After thematic group work at the EOSC Symposium, the six EOSC-A OAs were formed²⁰ in order to prepare the programme tracks for the EOSC Winter School²¹.

FAIRCORE4EOSC experts actively participated in shaping the Winter School sessions, especially OA1 and OA2, that were very closely related to the project topics. FAIRCORE4EOSC participated in the first EOSC Winter School in early 2024 in Thessaloniki, Greece. The idea was to strengthen the collaboration among the INFRAEOSC projects and deepen the mutual technical understanding in various “opportunity areas”. The EOSC OAs continued meeting and discussing on their respective topics after the EOSC Winter School. The contributions to the OAs during spring 2024 also worked as an “expert bridge” between the old EOSC TFs being closed at the end of 2023 and the establishment of new ones in June 2024.

2.2.1 OA1: Persistent Identifiers

The EOSC PID Policy²², originally developed by the EOSC FAIR Working Group and EOSC Architecture Working Group in 2020, serves as a foundational reference within FAIRCORE4EOSC, particularly in the design and implementation of various services—most notably the **CAT**. The evolution of the EOSC PID Policy, has been taken up from the PID Task Force in 2021 and within **OA1**, one of the seven thematic EOSC Opportunity Areas (OAs) established following the EOSC Symposium concentrates on persistent identifier (PID) infrastructures, and it continues the efforts of the previous EOSC Task Forces that concluded in 2023. We have to mention here that the Opportunity Areas are not formal EOSC-A bodies. Their outputs are considered community contributions rather than official EOSC deliverables. While OA outputs are informal by nature, they can still be picked up by structures within the EOSC Federation. The work that was done in the last year focuses on validating the PID Policy and creating a friendlier version with minor changes that reflect the needs of the communities. Based on that, during the third year of the project, members from FAIRCORE4EOSC project participated in the OA1 and are trying to support the update of the PID Policy based on input from the various communities that tested the services of the project. This participation played a key role in the revision and

¹⁷ OA1: Persistent Identifiers - EOSC Association

¹⁸ OA2: Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability - EOSC Association

¹⁹ OA7: Research Software - EOSC Association

²⁰ The initial EOSC task forces convened for 2 years, ending in the end of 2023. After the Madrid EOSC Symposium in 2023, the EOSC Focus project interviewed the different HE EOSC projects to identify the topics addressed by them. This showed the clusters of projects working on similar topics, and led to the foundation of 6 opportunity areas (OAs)

²¹ OAs have significant overlap in the topics to the TFs, and have partially been able to carry knowledge over the discontinuity point of the TFs stopping in the end of 2023 and then the establishment of new ones in the Autumn 2024.

²² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/35c5ca10-1417-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

development of PID Policy Version 2, ensuring that it reflects real-world needs gathered from the diverse communities who have tested FAIRCORE4EOSC services.

2.2.2 OA2: Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability

Opportunity Area 2 (OA2) deals with metadata, ontologies and interoperation. The work was kicked off during the EOSC Winter School 2024 in Thessaloniki, where the OA2 workshop gathered together participants from 16 EOSC projects. Two key organisers of the OA2 workshop were from FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT; the workshop preparation was a collaboration between the two projects. FAIRCORE4EOSC WP4 and especially the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry were actively presented and discussed. Based on discussions the FAIRCORE4EOSC and WP4 services are particularly well positioned to “map” together the current independent metadata/ontology modeling approaches from multiple projects. The MSCR got extra exposure in mappings related hands-on sessions.

2.2.3 OA7: Research Software

The EOSC-A's Opportunity Area Expert Group, OA7, addresses specific challenges and opportunities related to research software within the EOSC framework. Recognizing software as a crucial element—as a research tool, outcome, and object—OA7 emphasizes curation, quality assurance, preservation, and the adoption of best practices. It particularly highlights the importance of proper recognition and credit for software developers.

OA7 builds upon previous EOSC initiatives and collaborates with global partners like [SciCodes consortium](#), the [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#) and the [Research Data Alliance](#), to position research software as a fundamental element of science.

The expert group was launched in January 2025 with support from FAIRCORE4EOSC and is a way to disseminate the efforts done in FAIRCORE4EOSC for Research Software and continue the endeavour to make software a first-class research output.

2.3 EOSC Federation

During the third project year of FAIRCORE4EOSC the EOSC Tripartite launched the build-up of the EOSC Federation. During June - August 2024, the EOSC Tripartite ran a questionnaire to assess the interest in and readiness to participate in the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. This resulted in 121 submissions of which 29 organisations were identified and invited to participate in the dialogue phase. After the dialogue procedure 13 candidate nodes were selected, next to the EOSC EU Node, to join the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation, which started in March 2025. Different partners of FAIRCORE4EOSC contribute to the EOSC Federation build-up as a member of a candidate node organisation.

To guide the candidate nodes to join the EOSC Federation, the EOSC-A, in collaboration with the EOSC Tripartite Governance, started developing the *EOSC Federation Handbook* in September 2024. The aim of the EOSC Federation Handbook is detailing the EOSC Federation and Node concepts, the EOSC federating capabilities and the criteria for nodes to join the federation. After an intensive writing and consultation period during the September 2024 - February 2025, the first version EOSC Federation Handbook²³ was published in March 2025. Different representatives from FAIRCORE4EOSC partners have been participating either as a member of the writing (i.e. SURF, CSC) or reviewing (i.e. CSC, INRIA, OpenAIRE) team of the Federation handbook. The EOSC Federation handbook will be tested and updated during the build-up phase.

In general, the guidelines described in the EOSC Federation handbook describe that services and resources are made available through nodes within the federation. The organisations involved in the development and

²³ EOSC Association (2025) EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999576>

productization of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services have started to assess through which node a FAIRCORE4EOSC component can be sustained and made available for reasons described more in this deliverable.

2.3.1 EOSC Interoperability Framework

The EOSC Federation Handbook describes the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)²⁴ as a “key part of the EOSC Federation Architecture that compiles all standards, best practices and technical guidelines accepted by the Federation for the interoperability and composability of resources offered by the EOSC Nodes, including the EOSC Federating Capabilities”. The standards, best practices and technical guidelines are captured in so-called EOSC Interoperability Guidelines (EOSC IG) which are registered and promoted through the EOSC Interoperability Registry. The concept of the EOSC Interoperability Framework has been developed overtime through different EOSC-A Working Groups (FAIR and Architecture WG), Task Forces (Technical Interoperability Data and Services TF and the current Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF) and EOSC related projects (e.g. EOSC-Hub, EOSC Future).

Because the aim of FAIRCORE4EOSC is to develop EOSC Core services supporting FAIR, guidelines need to be provided on how the services can be used and/or integrated within community services or workflows.

Despite the fact that the EOSC Federation Handbook describes the EOSC Interoperability Registry as being operated by the EOSC EU Node as part of the Resource Hub²⁵, it only contains the EOSC IG onboarded during the EOSC Future project and there are at the time of writing this report no rules and procedures to onboard guidelines into the EOSC Interoperability Registry. The EOSC IF Governance will be defined during the build up phase of the Federation. Due to the lack of an EOSC IF Governance and clear rules and procedures to onboard IG into the EOSC IF registry, the guidelines developed within the project can not be promoted as EOSC Interoperability Guidelines. The interoperability guidelines are made available as documentation of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services.

2.3.2 Evolving EOSC-Core implementation

The initial concept of the EOSC-Core has been developed through the EOSC Sustainability and EOSC Architecture working groups as reported in *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC*²⁶ in 2020 and in the *EOSC architecture working group view on the minimum viable EOSC*²⁷ in 2021. A first implementation of the EOSC-Core was implemented by the EOSC Future project as an EOSC Platform offering the capabilities described in the EOSC Future *D3.2b EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework*²⁸ deliverable. The concept of the EOSC-Core as defined by the EOSC-A WGs and the implementation by the EOSC Future project have been the basis of the call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-03: Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR²⁹ and the FAIRCORE4EOSC proposal addressing the topics of this call.

²⁴ See EOSC Federation Handbook, section 4.4 The EOSC Interoperability Framework

²⁵ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/interoperability>

²⁶ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC – A FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>

²⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Sanden, M. v. d., Robertson, D., Appleton, O. et al., *EOSC architecture working group view on the minimum viable EOSC – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/492370>

²⁸ EOSC Future D2.9 Co-designed architecture description

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5e70906ed&applied=PPGMS>

²⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2021-eosc-01-03>

With the launch of building up the EOSC Federation, the procurement of the EOSC EU Node and the shutdown of the EOSC Platform (as developed and operated during the EOSC Future project), the FAIRCORE4EOSC work plan that was based on the EOSC-Core, was deemed to be impossible to implement. At the time of this writing (April 2025), the EOSC Federation Handbook does not describe the EOSC-Core in the context of the EOSC Federation. Interpreting section 4 *EOSC Federation and Node Architecture* of the EOSC Federation Handbook, the EOSC-Core concept has been replaced by the EOSC Federating Capabilities, as described in section 4.3 of the handbook. As described in section 2.3, the EOSC Tripartite Governance recently started the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. While section 4.3.1 of the EOSC Federation Handbook describes the *Federating Capabilities in the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation*, it does not describe how these Federation Capabilities are implemented or sustainably funded.

While the aim of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project is to extend the EOSC-Core with components supporting FAIR, **it is not clear how the FAIRCORE4EOSC services can be enabled as a Federating Capability within the EOSC Federation**. While section 4.3.2 of the EOSC Federation Handbook describes the possibility to extend the initial set of Federating Capabilities, it does not provide guidelines and/or criteria to establish a new Federating Capability, nor does it describe how these Federating Capabilities are sustainably funded. In order to maximise the investment done by the EC in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, clarity on the following points would be essential:

- Clarify the process and criteria to establish new Federating Capabilities within the EOSC Federation.
- Develop a sustainable funding model to maintain and operate a Federating Capability beyond the development through the HE WP funding calls.

2.4 HE INFRAEOSC Coordination

FAIRCORE4EOSC has taken part in the Horizon Europe (HE) working groups (WG) facilitated by the EOSC Focus project to gather the INFRAEOSC project representatives in thematic groups to share information, synchronise activities and collaborate. FAIRCORE4EOSC was involved in the Technology WG, Communication and Engagement WG, and Impact WG. Moreover, the project has participated actively in yearly HE INFRAEOSC Coordination Meetings held in Brussels, and contributed to the EOSC Macro Roadmap³⁰. These constellations have offered the project a possibility to share knowledge, network and take back to the project development work the lessons learned from the collaboration in the WGs.

2.4.1 HE INFRAEOSC Coordination Meetings

Horizon Europe (HE) INFRAEOSC coordination meetings are one of the various coordination mechanisms to keep the broad EOSC community engaged and moving forward towards the common goal of making EOSC a reality. These annual meetings are targeted at the ongoing projects funded under the INFRAEOSC destination of Horizon Europe Framework Programme and are organised by the European Commission (DG RTD, DG CNECT), the Research Executive Agency (REA) and the EOSC Association. The purpose of the HE INFRAEOSC coordination meetings is to inform the projects about the recent and upcoming EOSC developments, discuss and explore opportunities for collaboration and synergies among the projects, the EOSC Partnership and the broader EOSC community. The projects can propose agenda items in advance, ensuring that the meetings are inclusive and information flows in both directions – from the EOSC Partnership to the projects and vice versa. The limit of 2 representatives per project, means that the project representatives have more access to the European Commission staff, e.g. to discuss upcoming policy questions. The information received in the meetings can then be reported back to their consortia by the project representatives who can take this information into consideration in their project implementation strategies.

³⁰ [EOSC Macro-Roadmap - EOSC Association](#)

#1 Meeting with INFRAEOSC Projects 30 September 2022, Brussels

The first coordination meeting focused on how to organise the complex cooperation between the projects and the EOSC Partnership. The first version of the “[Vademecum, a Handbook for Effective Collaboration within the EOSC Co-Programmed Partnership](#)” had been distributed to the meeting participants before the meeting, detailing five areas of cooperation and alignment (Governance, Administration, Communication and Stakeholder Management, Monitoring Technical Developments). FAIRCORE4EOSC took notice of the document and shared it with the consortium. FAIRCORE4EOSC also tweaked the project branding to comply with the EOSC co-branding guidelines. The meeting provided a good opportunity for networking and getting a better understanding of other projects’ activities as well as introduction to the emerging coordination scheme for the EOSC community.

Impact:

- Networking with INFRAEOSC projects and the EOSC Partnership
- Information about the status of EOSC and the emerging coordination framework for the EOSC community
- Redo of the FAIRCORE4EOSC visual look based on the new EOSC Association co-branding guidelines³¹
- Following the meeting, FAIRCORE4EOSC appointed project representatives to the Horizon Europe Working Groups (read more in 2.4.2, 2.4.3 and 2.4.4)

#2 Meeting with INFRAEOSC Projects 15-16 June 2023, Brussels

The second coordination meeting sought to consolidate and advance discussions held in the previous year and gave the floor to the new projects funded under the 2022 HE calls (starting in 2023) to present their project plans. The EOSC-A and the supporting project EOSC Focus presented the EOSC macro-roadmap, that had been designed to capture the contributions from the INFRAEOSC projects and other actors to depict concretely how the EOSC implementation progresses over time. Furthermore, FAIRCORE4EOSC together with FAIR-IMPACT and some other projects raised the challenge of how hard it is to compile sustainability and exploitation plans for project results in the EOSC landscape that is changing and developing so fast.

The meeting also stressed the fact that a one- or two-day meeting with a limited number of project representatives was not enough to go into the details of solving the technical and other subject-matter-oriented questions of the EOSC implementation, but are more a place for making first contacts. Consequently, the idea of the EOSC Winter Schools for more technical collaboration originated from discussion in the 2023 coordination meeting, to complement these coordination meetings.

Impact:

- Networking with INFRAEOSC projects and the EOSC Partnership
- Information about the advancement towards an operational EOSC federation and the novelties in the coordination framework for the EOSC community (See the EOSC macro-roadmap in 2.4.5).
- Following the meeting,
 - FAIRCORE4EOSC services were published on the EOSC macro-roadmap
 - FAIRCORE4EOSC provided input to EOSC Winter School planning and later participated in it

³¹ <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Co-Branding-Guidelines-for-HE-INFRAEOSC-Projects.pdf>

- Experts active in FAIRCORE4EOSC joined the OA1PIDs and OA2 Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability creating a useful connection between the project and the broader discussions and work in the OAs.

#3 Meeting with INFRAEOSC Projects 20-21 June 2024, Brussels

The third coordination meeting revolved around the topic of the EOSC Federation. DG CNECT and the EU Node contractors gave a status update of the development of the EOSC EU Node, and DG RTD, EOSC-A, EOSC Steering Board presented how the implementation of the Federation was foreseen to progress.

Impact:

- Networking with INFRAEOSC projects and the EOSC Partnership
- Information about the EOSC Federation and the EOSC EU node further confirmed the facts that the FAIRCORE4EOSC services could not be part of the concept of EOSC Core as originally planned and directed the sustainability plans towards other options (See FAIRCORE4EOSC D7.3 *Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities*).

2.4.2 HE Technology Working Group

Horizon Europe Technology Group (HE Technology) gathers together the key technical coordination staff from the INFRAEOSC projects in monthly virtual meetings where they focus on high-level technical coordination - sharing information from the association to the projects and from the projects to all the other participants. This group is a key source of information on relevant topics in the EOSC community e.g. on the development of the procurement, developments regarding the federation, but has also discussed most current events such as the Symposia, winter school preparations and the OAs. It also receives occasional updates from the TFs, and the work of FAIRCORE4EOSC has also been presented there. A physical meeting was also organised as the EOSC Technical Coordinators' Cockpit meeting at the Madrid EOSC Symposium in September 2023.

In a way this forum works as an extension of the HE INFRAEOSC Coordination Meetings, allowing for more frequent topical updates on current matters. FAIRCORE4EOSC has been an active participant in these meetings, and has used this forum to make its activities well known throughout the EOSC projects.

2.4.3 HE Communication and Engagement Working Group

The Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Working Group (HE C&E WG) supports better coordination of communication and stakeholder engagement activities between INFRAEOSC projects e.g. to avoid clashes of project events. It also encourages projects to use the EOSC Forum— a shared space where projects exchange information about upcoming events, consultations, and communication activities involving all EOSC-related projects and stakeholders.

HE C&E WG allowed FAIRCORE4EOSC to stay closely connected with other Horizon Europe projects working on EOSC, making sure the project was well integrated into the wider EOSC ecosystem and on top of the stakeholder engagement activities of other projects to avoid targeting the same audiences for similar activities. The project could also reach broader audiences by joining forces with other projects for outreach activities e.g. by cross-promoting each other's activities. Through the EOSC Forum and the monthly meetings, FAIRCORE4EOSC could share project news and updates, and invite other projects to project events such as the FAIRfest.

2.4.4 HE Impact Working Group

The Horizon Europe Impact Working Group (HE Impact WG) is a working group focussing on collecting and analysing Key Exploitable Results (KERs) from the HE projects. Therefore, also collecting and analysing the KERs from FAIRCORE4EOSC. FAIRCORE4EOSC has been engaged with the HE Impact WG since the EOSC Winterschool 2024³², at which the HE Impact WG organised a workshop on *Sustainable Exploitation Pathways to Exploitation of Key Results* for INFRAEOSC projects. After some introductory presentations to set the scene, the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP)³³ methodology was introduced which has been developed by the EOSC Focus project. The SEP methodology provides a model for the HE projects to develop sustainability plans for their KERs.

After the introduction of the SEP model at the EOSC Winterschool 2024, FAIRCORE4EOSC planned to adopt this model to develop the exploitation for the project and the individual sustainability plans for the FAIRCORE4EOSC services. As a starting point to develop the sustainability plans a session was held at the second FAIRCORE4EOSC Technical Project Meeting, on *Developing sustainability plans for FAIRCORE4EOSC services*. The session was organised in collaboration with EOSC Focus. The development teams used the SEP survey tool to start the thinking process to develop sustainability plans for the FAIRCORE4EOSC services. The results of this exercise will be reported in *D7.3 Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities*.

2.4.5 EOSC Macro Roadmap

The EOSC Macro-Roadmap is an online catalogue of the outputs delivered by the EOSC projects and other relevant stakeholders active in the EOSC implementation (e.g. EOSC-A Task Forces). The outputs are mapped against the SRIA Action Areas and presented on a timeline to identify potential gaps in the EOSC implementation priorities and visualise what the community has already delivered and what is coming up next. The outputs are described in a short and easily understandable way because the macro-roadmap is meant to inform the entire EOSC community and the general audience. Each output on the macro-roadmap has a direct link to the respective output itself, and where feasible, also links to relevant additional information sources. Only the outputs related to the SRIA Action Areas are considered, excluding project-specific procedural documents such as project communication plans etc. The EOSC Macro-Roadmap was set up by the EOSC Association in 2023 and is available at <https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap/>.

Each FAIRCORE4EOSC service has been published on the macro-roadmap with up-to-date links to the services together with some additional links that help the web site visitor to understand how the tool/service works. Keeping this content up-to-date after FAIRCORE4EOSC ends, is based on the benevolence of the service developing organisations and dependent on the success of sustainability plans.

3. Horizon Europe Projects (mostly INFRAEOSC)

FAIRCORE4EOSC have aimed to find synergies with other INFRAEOSC projects by either identifying them at the very beginning and preparing alignment activities with some of them already at the proposal preparation phase or by onboarding the alignment activities during the implementation phase of the project. The engagement with the projects, introduced in this chapter has allowed FAIRCORE4EOSC to co-design different project outputs, receive feedback and share information. The level of engagement has varied overall as for example engagements planned already at the proposal phase have ensured there are resources to conduct such alignment activities with other projects but not everything can be planned and identified already at the proposal writing phase. Also, the different levels of maturity of other projects add an additional layer of

³² <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2024/>

³³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/SEPSurvey2024>

challenge, reflected in the level of alignment. However, overall engagement and strategic alignment is very useful to find synergies and to ensure work does not happen in silos.

Chapter three will introduce the strategic alignment activities of the FAIRCORE4EOSC towards other INFRAEOSC projects during the project life-cycle. The lessons learnt about the engagement with other projects are reported in chapter 6.

The table 2 summarises the engagement of FAIRCORE4EOSC with other projects.

Table 2: Projects with whom FAIRCORE4EOSC collaborated

Project title	Link to the Cordis page
FAIR-IMPACT	https://doi.org/10.3030/101057344
RAISE	https://doi.org/10.3030/101058479
GraspOS	https://doi.org/10.3030/101095129
RDA Tiger	https://doi.org/10.3030/101094406
EOSC Beyond	https://doi.org/10.3030/101131875
OSTrails	https://doi.org/10.3030/101130187
EVERSE	https://doi.org/10.3030/101129744
EOSC Focus	https://doi.org/10.3030/101058432
BIODT	https://doi.org/10.3030/101057437

3.1 FAIR-IMPACT

[FAIR-IMPACT](#)³⁴ is a Horizon Europe project, supporting European and national level implementation of practices, tools and services, such as metadata, PIDs and metrics, enabling FAIR and promoting their wider uptake. The project has been a close partner for FAIRCORE4EOSC as its role as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) to support FAIR-enabling tools and practices in turn supports FAIRCORE4EOSC with contacts to stakeholders and overall visibility with regards to the nine services developed and operationalized by FAIRCORE4EOSC. More concretely, partnering up with this “sister” project has enabled FAIRCORE4EOSC wider access to repositories, research communities and other stakeholders which allows the co-design of the services.

During the course of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, the two projects have engaged in a multitude of activities together, ranging from stakeholder activities and engagement to topics of technical alignment on themes of common interest. The project coordinators of both projects have met regularly in the course of the project to ensure strategic alignment. In addition, the alignment between the two projects have been ensured by FAIR-

³⁴ [FAIR-IMPACT: Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC | FAIR-IMPACT](#)

IMPACT participation in FAIRCORE4EOSC project meetings and vice versa as well as through bilateral collaboration on technical issues on work package level, in the Technical Bridging Team.

FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT have not only discussed bilaterally but also engaged with other INFRA-EOSC projects and EOSC partnership jointly by e.g. partaking in different EOSC Association Opportunity Areas and Task Forces (more on the FAIRCORE4EOSC engagement on EOSC partnerships on chapter 2) as well as co-organised a RDA working group on FAIR-MAPPINGS. In addition, during the project, FAIRCORE4EOSC has sought support for the uptake of the nine services beyond the project case studies by leveraging the support programme of FAIR-IMPACT. In this context CAT, MSCR and DTR have been featured in open FAIR-IMPACT support calls to support the adoption by new users. This collaboration has been of high strategic value for FAIRCORE4EOSC, as the support action has been able to fund the most eager adopters of DTR and MSCR, who are coming from outside the project. This was also an initially unplanned collaboration that was implemented when the opportunity presented itself. Testers have also been recruited jointly with FAIR-IMPACT to the RSAC services.

FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT representatives together submitted a proposal for personnel support for establishing a FAIR MAPPINGS working group (WG) in the RDA to the RDA Tiger project. The proposal was successfully evaluated, and FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT representatives have together created a draft charter for the WG. The WG will create a unifying classification of mappings that builds on existing classifications such as RDA Brokering Framework and Semantic Mapping Vocabulary (SEMAPV).

Beyond technical matters, the two projects have collaborated on stakeholder engagement and case study dissemination activities as well as promoted FAIRCORE4EOSC services in close collaboration to ensure maximal uptake of the services. Examples of such activities include joint webinars and events, promotion of each other's activities as well as organization of the very successful joint final event, FAIRfest, in the Hague, Netherlands (February 2025).

All in all, the alignment of the two projects has resulted in co-design of the services developed in both projects and wider uptake of the results developed within both projects through joint promotion of the products. Moreover, partnering up with FAIR-IMPACT has resulted in joint influencing and positioning towards EOSC landscape developments and contributions to the overall scientific community. E.g. after the 2024 EOSC Symposium, the two projects initiated a dialogue on sustainability of project outputs between the 2021 INFRAEOSC projects who all share this concern and the EOSC Association. In a more practical sense, the project has largely benefitted from some partners being involved in both of the projects, resulting in higher sharing of information between the projects and the ability to co-design activities such as the joint project kick-off and final meeting. However, those FAIRCORE4EOSC partners without involvement in both projects, or without engagement with FAIR-IMPACT partners in other forums, such as RDA, have had less regular contact points with the FAIR-IMPACT project.

3.2 RAISE

RAISE³⁵ develops a blockchain based technology to ensure that users can trust that analysis results are based on a given dataset, even when the data may not be shared for peer review and result verification. RAI - Research Analysis Identifier, could potentially form a new node type for the SKGs (PIDGraph, RDgraph) being developed in FC4E. In an attempt to identify project related synergies and understand each other's work, discussions were initiated at the EOSC projects Brussels meeting in 2023, and a consequent visit of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Coordinator was made to VICOMTECH in San Sebastian in November 2023. Further, FAIRCORE4EOSC invited RAISE to present their work to the CRIS community at the dedicated FAIRCORE4EOSC session in the euroCRIS

³⁵ [Research Analysis Identifier SystEm | RAISE | Projekt | Fact Sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission](#)

Strategic Membership Meeting in Pamplona Spain Nov 21-23 2023. Consequently, both projects followed this up with presentations of their work at the much larger euroCRIS Conference in May 2024.

3.3 GraspOS

The GraspOS project³⁶ aims to build and operate a data infrastructure to support institutions in the adoption of new Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) practices that recognize and reward contributions to Open Science, thereby also supporting the adoption of EOSC³⁷. The GraspOS-FAIRCORE4EOSC collaboration is focused on development of RAiD in FC4E, which is being used to underpin piloting of three services under development in the GraspOS Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF). The services are (1) an Assessment Portfolio and (2) Assessment Registry, both of which aimed at facilitating research assessment reform (CoARA³⁸); as well as (3) the Openness Profile, which aims to support researchers in making visible their contributions to Open Science. GraspOS and FAIRCORE4EOSC also share research.fi as part of a case study in FC4E and a pilot in GraspOS, which brings synergies.

In this collaboration, GraspOS was granted access to the RAiD demo, which informed development of the three services noted above. The Openness Profile service in particular will be included in four of the GraspOS pilots. Access to the RAiD demo and associated documentation has enabled the following:

- mapping the RAiD metadata scheme to other GraspOS services
- potential extension of the RAiD schema to accommodate research assessment
- exploration of implementing the RAiD API in a national CRIS
- exploration of implementing the RAiD API in other GraspOS services

GraspOS aims to deliver a federated infrastructure, which will support research assessment processes by integrating and providing easy access to a range of resources, including data, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials—including the three RAiD-based services addressed above.

3.4 Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions (RDA TIGER)

FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT representatives together submitted a proposal for personnel support for establishing a FAIR MAPPINGS working group (WG) in the RDA to the RDA Tiger project³⁹. The proposal was successfully evaluated, and FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT representatives have together written, with support from the RDA Tiger staff, a draft charter for the WG. The WG was endorsed (founded) in the spring 2025. This WG essentially brings together an international and multi-disciplinary audience of potential MSCR adopters. RDA Tiger has continued to support the activities towards the formation of the FAIR Mappings WG through several kick-off meetings, revisions of the case statement and finally organization and communication related to the activities of an endorsed group.

RDA TIGER has been able to reuse software developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC (CAT) to develop the [RDA Knowledge Base](#), which is in beta operation and adds to the software sustainability of the code base for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit.

³⁶ [GraspOS, https://graspos.eu/](https://graspos.eu/)

³⁷ Pillar 1 of the Multi-Annual Roadmap, which forms Section 8 of the SRIA, <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>

³⁸ <https://coara.eu/>

³⁹ [RDA Tiger | Research Software Directory](#)

3.5 EOSC Beyond

EOSC Beyond⁴⁰ is one of the INFRA-EOSC projects that started in 2024. The aim of EOSC Beyond is to extend the EOSC Core by improving existing (EOSC Future -era) EOSC Core services and delivering three new services that will be tested and validated by pilot Nodes. Because EOSC Beyond is, similar to FAIRCORE4EOSC, developing new EOSC Core service, there is a natural interest from FAIRCORE4EOSC to engage with EOSC Beyond. FAIRCORE4EOSC established contact with EOSC Beyond from early on and invited the project to FAIRCORE4EOSC technical project meeting (04/2024 Athens) where Mark Dietrich, EGI, gave a presentation on EOSC Beyond’s ambitions regarding the distributed EOSC core. Due to the introduction of the EOSC Federation, the project meeting provided an opportunity to discuss the changes within the concept of the EOSC Core, disabling FAIRCORE4EOSC to offer the services as EOSC Core services and/or to integrate with the EOSC Core capabilities. This led to the conclusion that a pathway forward to validate the readiness of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services to be integrated within the EOSC Federating capabilities was to validate the integration with the EOSC Beyond Innovation Sandbox. To discuss the use and integration of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services with the EOSC Beyond EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, FAIRCORE4EOSC organised a workshop between both projects at the EUDAT Conference on the 4-5 December 2024, Karlsruhe, Germany, see section 5.1.2.

3.5.1 EOSC Beyond workshops

10th to 12th of June 2024, a workshop was held by the EOSC Beyond Project, in Krakow Poland to assist those communities enrolled in the EOSC Beyond that were developing an EOSC pilot node, to on the one hand test the node onboarding criteria and process under development in EOSC Beyond, and on the other hand develop their own activities towards nodeship. FAIRCORE4EOSC was invited to the event hosted by project partner Cyfronet, in order to help the project to figure out how to substitute the originally intended EOSC Core integration by a new approach. The concept of FAIRCORE4EOSC becoming an EOSC pilot node was also initially discussed, but turned out to be infeasible, due to the financial sustainability requirements that a fixed term project is not likely to meet. The concept of integrating instead with the EOSC Beyond Sandbox arose from here, as many of the former EOSC Future -era core services continue to be made accessible there in a non-production environment.

To further support the collaboration between FAIRCORE4EOSC and the EOSC Beyond project and to discuss the use EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox developed by EOSC Beyond, FAIRCORE4EOSC organised a workshop between both projects at the EUDAT Conference on the 4-5 December 2024, Karlsruhe, Germany. The workshop was organised as one day workshop, spread across two days.

After introductory presentations from EOSC Beyond and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects, to learn the main aims and scope of the projects, a deep dive session was organised to learn about the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox services and integration options. On the next day a hands-on session was organised to further discuss and evaluate the integration options for the different services. At the start of the hands-on session the interest was gauged from the integration options between FAIRCORE4EOSC services and Sandbox capabilities, most interest was on the federated AAI, Monitoring and Helpdesk services. Therefore, during the hands-on session, the focus was on the integration with the AAI, Monitoring, Helpdesk Sandbox services. After the workshop, the development teams did further testing with the sandbox capabilities.

3.5.2 EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox

The aim of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox⁴¹, developed by the EOSC Beyond project, aims to provide a comprehensive testbed environment equipped with advanced automation tools designed for the testing and

⁴⁰ [Homepage - EOSC Beyond](#)

⁴¹ <https://sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/>

validation of EOSC services. It serves two primary purposes: prototyping enhanced and new EOSC Core services, and allowing providers to validate their integration with the EOSC before deploying services into production. The EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox provides the following Federating Capabilities: AAI, Accounting, Execution Framework, Helpdesk, Integration Suite, Messaging, Monitoring, PID, Resource Catalogue, Order Management and User Space. From the offered Federating Capabilities, testing the integration with the Federated AAI was requested by most development teams. Some development teams also tested the integration with the Helpdesk and Monitoring capability. During the discussions, and how the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox is offered, it became clear that the Innovation Sandbox could only be used for testing and not for production purposes. Because the aim of the FAIRCORE4EOSC is to offer production services it was not possible to use any of the Innovation Sandbox capabilities in production. It also became clear that there was no pathway offered to move from the Innovation Sandbox to an instance of the Federating Capabilities which could be used for production purposes. Therefore, the development teams still needed to find solutions to run the services in production, for example to integrate with EUDAT B2ACCESS⁴² Infrastructure Proxy to enable federated logins through eduGAIN. While it is good to test and validate the integration with the EOSC Federating Capabilities, if there is no clear pathway to migrate from testing to production, it reduces the usefulness of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox.

3.6 OSTrails

OSTrails⁴³ focuses on the planning, discovery and assessment of scientific information with an emphasis on connecting services that support such actions so that the data that they hold can be automatically and seamlessly exchanged between them facilitating researchers' workflows. These services are Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), Data Management Planning platforms (DMPs) and FAIR assessment tools. CAT service from FAIRCORE4EOSC has helped in shaping a common point of reference for terminology used between the two projects, essential to modelling FAIR assessments and tests. (align the information and conceptual models, vocabularies to the maximum possible extent to ensure harmonisation between the Toolkit and major FAIR evaluation services. Enable the Toolkit to serve as an aggregator and publication platform for FAIR assessments.) FAIRCORE4EOSC partner OpenAIRE coordinates OSTrails, which helps with flow of communication.

DANS is involved in the OSTRAILS project, and will endeavour to deploy an instance of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit for integration with OSTRAILS tool APIs that meets the harmonisation specifications developed in that project. This work will be continued after the conclusion of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

In time, it will also make sense to ensure that the CAT Knowledge Base implements an API that is compatible with the SKG-IF specifications being developed jointly in OSTRAILS and RDA.

3.7 EVERSE

The strategic alignment activity between FAIRCORE4EOSC and EVERSE⁴⁴ focuses on fostering collaborative efforts towards research software support, thereby significantly advancing Open Science goals. A MoU between the two projects was signed in November 2024.

The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities, in pursuit of building a European network of Research Software Quality and setting the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

⁴² <https://eudat.eu/service-catalogue/b2access>

⁴³ [About - OSTrails](#)

⁴⁴ [EVERSE](#)

The goal of the agreement between the two projects is to align and adopt developed tools and services for archival, reference, description and citation of research software artefacts. Discussions within the framework of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) target the joint adoption and integration of services and tools dedicated to archival, referencing, description, and citation of research software artifacts.

Collaboration highlights include:

- Alignment and adherence to EOSC SIRS report recommendations.
- Promotion of interoperability using Software Heritage intrinsic identifiers - Software Hash IDs (SWHIDs) and CodeMeta metadata standards.
- Enhanced accessibility to research software artifacts and source code.
- Contributions towards achieving the interconnected scholarly ecosystem envisioned by EOSC's SRIA.
- Preparatory activities for EVERSE's review of FAIRCORE4EOSC's deliverable D6.1 on standardization and curation of software metadata and persistent identifiers (PIDs).
- Access provided by FAIRCORE4EOSC to the beta version of the Research Software Archival Connector (RSAC), particularly the InvenioRDM-SWH connector.
- Organization of joint internal calls, public workshops, and webinars to share expertise and strengthen community involvement.

This collaboration between FAIRCORE4EOSC and EVERSE amplifies the impact of both projects, further supporting the long-term sustainability of research software infrastructures within the EOSC ecosystem.

3.8 Biodiversity Digital Twin (BioDT)

The Horizon Europe Project "Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities (BioDT)" (101057437) aims to develop the game engine to address biodiversity grand challenges like biodiversity loss due to climate change and increasing land use, the radiation of alien invasive species as well as the spreading of zoonotic and vector-based diseases. These Biodiversity Digital Twins (each representing the real-world entities and processes of the aforementioned use cases at specified frequencies and fidelities in cyberspace) are complemented by other thematic Digital Twins (e.g. DT Smart Cities or DT Extreme Natural Disasters) within the wider framework of the comprehensive Earth simulation framework DestinE⁴⁵. The BioDT-project mobilises biodiversity Big Data from environmental-related European (ENVRI community⁴⁶) and global research infrastructures involving in particular DiSSCo⁴⁷, LifeWatch ERIC⁴⁸, eLTER⁴⁹ and GBIF⁵⁰ for state-of-the-art-modelling on HPC platforms such as EuroHPC JU's LUMI⁵¹. Integration of biodiversity data from heterogeneous sources including sensor-based monitoring tools like camera traps (Jansen 2020⁵²) requires consistent mappings between different trait and environmental ontologies (Karam 2020⁵³). The FAIRCORE4EOSC engagement with the BioDT project has resulted in the FAIRCORE4EOSC

⁴⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

⁴⁶ <https://envri.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.dissco.eu/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://elter-ri.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁵¹ <https://research.csc.fi/service/lumi-supercomputer/>

⁵² Jansen M, Engler M, Blumer LM, Rumiz DI, Aramayo JL, Krone O (2020) A camera trapping survey of mammals in the mixed landscape of Bolivia's Chiquitano region with a special focus on the Jaguar. Check List 16(2): 323-335. <https://doi.org/10.15560/16.2.323>

⁵³ Karam, N., Khat, A., Algergawy, A., Sattler, M., Weiland, C., & Schmidt, M. (2020). Matching biodiversity and ecology ontologies: Challenges and evaluation results. The Knowledge

supporting BioDT in using the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) to pilot, for example the creation and registration of a crosswalk between DCAT 3.0 and Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0) schema as an example of schema mapping as well as exploring the possibility of registering an entity mapping (FDO type of SSSOM) created with mapping.bio-tool⁵⁴ developed in the BioDT project. As a result, MCSR was presented at the TDWG conference in Australia in October 2023⁵⁵

A Letter of Intent (to collaborate) between FAIRCORE4EOSC and the Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities (BioDt, project number 101057437, HORIZON-RIA) was signed in May 2023 to formalise the collaboration and align the activities.

Both the FAIRCORE4EOSC and BioDT projects will end in spring 2025, but the proposed use cases have been identified as an important topic to be continued with future collaboration and development. As environmental and biodiversity data require ways to integrate data across domains and from very heterogeneous sources, the use of MCSR for collaboration has a high demand in the international environment RI landscape.

4. Strategic communities

Finally, the project has also carried out alignment activities with other strategic communities both at the European and global level. The rationale for such alignment activities have been to ensure that the services developed in the project are applicable in the communities that might end up adopting the services. Moreover, some of these communities have been represented in the project itself in the case study work.

The added benefit of expanding the alignment outside of the project is to ensure the services developed within FAIRCORE4EOSC are applicable to other instances, such as the scope of other projects outside EOSC. To formalise some of these alignment activities, FAIRCORE4EOSC have prepared Memorandum of Understandings (MoUs) and Letters of Intent (LoIs) with other projects, BioDT and SWITCH. The alignment activities with these two projects have been utilised to further develop MCSR service, developed within the WP4 of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. Moreover, a GWDG, partner in FAIRCORE4EOSC project submitted a PIDinst proposal to further develop Data Type Registry (DTR) service by aligning DFG activities. Albeit the proposal was not funded, the work continued in the end. The overall impact of the alignment has been great as it has enabled wider visibility of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services outside of the HE and EOSC realm and the ability to test the project outputs.

This chapter will demonstrate the strategic alignment activities of FAIRCORE4EOSC that have taken place outside of the EOSC and Horizon Europe realms.

4.1 ENES Climate Modelling Community

The significant and wide-ranging consequences of human-made climate change have made it one of the most pressing issues of our time. The entire ‘ecosystem’ of climate research, with the climate model simulations as a core element, is based on the fundamental idea of open science. The need for services that enhance the discoverability and reusability of research results is thus critical.

As part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, we evaluated within the Case Study ‘Climate Change’ how the new FAIRCORE4EOSC services can benefit the Climate Community. The ENES (European Network for Earth System

Engineering Review, 35, E9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0269888920000132>

⁵⁴ Wolodkin A, Weiland C, Grieb J (2023) Mapping.bio: Piloting FAIR semantic mappings for biodiversity digital twins. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 7: e111979. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.111979>

⁵⁵ Making Schemas and Mappings Available and FAIR: A metadata and schema crosswalk registry from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.112223>

Modeling)⁵⁶ research infrastructure was selected as a test environment due to its broad range of climate research data from national and international projects associated with different funding streams.

The data within ENES research infrastructure (ENES-RI) are extensive, and a typical use case to be considered is the creation of downstream data products. In this context, provenance information about the used data plays a crucial role to understand where the data originated from, how data has been processed, or even reprocessed. Additionally, the project context, involved institutions and individuals, related publications, and connections between the data are also of great importance. Another key aspect is the automation of downstream data product creation, especially considering the large data volumes that need to be processed. Practical and efficient solutions for structuring and cataloging data in a machine-readable format are of great importance. Specifically, the relationship between DOIs and related datasets is often not represented in common available knowledge graphs, making machine-based reuse more challenging.

ENES provides data and provenance information for dataset-associated PIDs, which are linked to lower granularity data collections to which DOIs are assigned. During FAIRCORE4EOSC, those DOIs were harvested by and made available in the PIDGraph and RDGraph services. The assignment of DOIs to RAIDs allows improved linkage and discoverability of research activities. The metadata schema associated with ENES PIDs was registered at the DTR and in this way now supports machine parsing methods – also important for processing large data volumes. Using the MSCR, it's possible to analyse different PID metadata definitions by mapping them, making them easier to compare. In addition, these mapping analyses could be made machine-actionable, enabling work on large volumes of data. As a result, the integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC services provides a broader view of the data used.

Climate researchers, associated communities and policy makers will benefit from the new services produced by the project through improved discoverability and reusability of data collections at several levels of granularity and the allocation of data to experiments and projects in ENES. The full impact will only materialise when the new services are ready and available for end-users in the long-term and in a sustainable manner, allowing a greater level of FAIRness of research outputs compared to the current state. For the ENES community, the better linkage of datasets and their metadata to projects through RAIDs as well as the specification of the community PID profile in the DTR were perceived as particularly useful. The improved linkage will lead to better findability of the data by climate impact communities and stakeholders via PID and RDGraph. It will also help authors of assessment reports, e.g. the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) reports⁵⁷, which comprehensively informs policy makers about impact and mitigation measures of climate change.

We see several opportunities of facilitating operational workflows of the ENES community with the above mentioned services, albeit e.g. the resilient uptake for the upcoming CMIP7 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project)⁵⁸ workflows largely depend on the timely finalisation and adaptation of the services and on many other largely external factors such as services' sustainability and community stakeholder decisions. An ongoing challenge for ENES is to improve interoperability and machine actionability between data spaces, e.g. observational and simulated data, in climate science. We want to tackle this task by registering and specifying STAC catalogs⁵⁹ in the DTR and implementing them as FDOs⁶⁰, which enables interoperable and automated access.

⁵⁶ Main website for the Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling project, <https://is.enes.org/index.html>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ipcc.ch/reports/>

⁵⁸ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phases/cmip7/>

⁵⁹ <https://stacspec.org/en>

⁶⁰ <https://fairdo.org/>

4.2 CLARIN Community

The CLARIN community is driving the Social Sciences and Humanities case study within FAIRCORE4EOSC. In their heterogeneous domain different services, specific to the various subdomains, are encountered that manage a wide variety of metadata, data types, and tools. Making such services and data interoperable with services from other domains would encourage cross-discipline alignment in service development and contribute to the realization of "horizontal" services across sciences. The main goal for this case study is to further improve the discoverability and interoperability of data and services within and across the SSH domain.

The case study's recent interoperability advancements closely reflect its commitment to the FAIR principles. This also fits well into the EOSC Interoperability Framework, particularly in the area of technical interoperability for APIs and data formats. Key achievements include integration with the PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR), the Data Type Registry (DTR), and the Metadata Schema Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), all central services of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The Digital Object Gateway⁶¹ (DOG), which provides a uniform API across CLARIN services and diverse PID and repository systems, was integrated with the DTR to enable support for extended mime-types and taxonomies. This not only enhances interoperability but also benefits services like the Language Resource Switchboard⁶² (LRS) by facilitating richer, machine-actionable data flows.

The Virtual Collection Registry⁶³ (VCR), a tool for managing virtual collections that link to distributed resources, is integrated with three FAIRCORE4EOSC services: PIDMR, DTR, and MSCR. It supports resolution of approximately 10 new PID systems, including various URN:NBN formats and arXiv identifiers, thus improving both identifier interoperability and findability. Moreover, its integration with the MSCR enables support to process external metadata schemas when referencing resources in a collection. Availability of relevant schemas and crosswalks is a precursor for the usefulness of this integration. This underlines the importance of broad MSCR adoption and maturity for enhancing metadata interoperability.

These developments not only improve technical infrastructure but also demonstrate CLARIN's alignment with the FAIR principles, especially in terms of accessibility and interoperability, and its active contribution to realizing the goals of the EOSC Interoperability Framework. Ways to continue these developments are being pursued. Both the DOG and LRS play an important role in the ATRIUM and ECHOES projects and will continue to benefit from the FAIRCORE4EOSC integration work.

4.3 EuroCRIS

euroCRIS is an international not-for-profit association that brings together experts on research information management and research information management systems. In addition, the association maintains and develops the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF), which is intended to support research information exchange between different CRIS systems. The CERIF as a common schema plays a major role in utilizing the MSCR as a way to support the possible system-to-system data exchanges in the CRIS community (Kesäniemi et al., 2024⁶⁴). Thus, the MSCR as a tool for supporting extensive interoperability remains important within euroCRIS community and will be explored further in this context.

⁶¹ <https://beta-dog.clarin.eu/>

⁶² <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>

⁶³ <https://collections.clarin.eu/>

⁶⁴ Kesäniemi, Joonas & Suominen, Tommi & Ivanović, Dragan & Dvorak, Jan. (2024). CRIS systems integration as a case study for the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry. *Procedia Computer Science*. 249. 243-253. 10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.070.

euroCRIS is also a highly relevant stakeholder group as CRIS systems can be either consumers of or providers for the research graphs (OpenAIRE, PIDGraph). Enhancing these global research graphs with well curated organisational CRIS data has been identified as an important source of verified research information. In contrast, these global services are great sources for linking research outputs and organisations together in graph-like manner, which might have been difficult otherwise to bring in local or national CRIS systems.

When RAiDs are more widely adopted, they may in the future be highly relevant for CRIS systems in linking the input (people, organisations, funding) to research outputs (publications, datasets, activities). euroCRIS community has shown great interest in taking RAiD into use while at the same time providing ideas for the possible governance and policy related issues that may arise in implementing RAiD.

Recognizing research software and its source code as a distinct research output—beyond being treated as just another dataset—is increasingly important for CRIS systems. While there have been preliminary discussions within the euroCRIS community to integrate this new type of entity, current support in Software Heritage for research-related persistent identifiers (PIDs), such as ORCID for individuals and ROR for organizations, remains limited. That said, it is already possible to include ORCID and ROR information in CodeMeta files within code repositories, although the responsibility currently falls on researchers to do so manually.

4.4 EUDAT

Some partners in FAIRCORE4EOSC are members of the [EUDAT CDI](#) and participate in many European projects and provide research data management tools to research communities like B2SHARE, B2DROP, B2ACCESS, B2SAFE, B2FIND & B2HANDLE. FAIRCORE4EOSC had high visibility in the EUDAT conferences in 2022 in Athens and in 2024 in Karlsruhe showcasing its work in the plenary sessions. In the first one served to inform about the work that was to be done, and in the latter one to showcase the work that was done. In the Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities (SPRDM) case study, EUDAT CDI’s B2SHARE and B2FIND were to be enhanced and improved through integration of the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), Data Type Registry (DTR), Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) and Persistent Identifiers (PIDGraph), Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) and Compliance Assessment Tool (CAT) services.

EUDAT Extended (B2SHARE) and EUDAT Core (B2FIND) metadata schemas were defined and registered to MSCR and DTR. For B2SHARE, data type definition handling through DTR seems a valuable method, which hopefully can be expanded in future. Collaborative editing of crosswalks hopefully reduces mapping and communication efforts between EUDAT services and communities as the number of defined schemas and crosswalks increases. Persistent identifiers within metadata referring RDGraph, PIDGraph and RAiD will make it easier to enrich information on research for datasets available and discoverable in B2SHARE and B2FIND, and thus propagate to other repositories sharing or referencing to their information - research activities, projects, citations and related data sources. EOSC PID compatibility was assessed and passed for B2SHARE using the CAT, and we hope to see several other policies to be available for compliance testing in future.

As it was for all Case Studies, for EUDAT CDI services, maturity and sustainability of the services is very important when integrating them to production environments. There was a big difference in terms of maturity between the offered services. This made the integration work for these services challenging and the Case Studies have opted for conservative integration strategies. These strategies ranged from merely piloting the services to assess their usability and only really integrate them at a later point in time to implementing alternative strategies for when the services are not available or functioning as expected and therefore not stopping the end-user workflow.

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit has prepared a draft sustainability plan with the objective of deploying the software as an operational service or service suite in EUDAT. The planning has been included into deliverable D2.3. For other services, such prospects are addressed in the upcoming deliverable D7.3.

4.5 Research Data Alliance (RDA)

Many partners in FAIRCORE4EOSC actively participate in the international research community that is RDA and its many working groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs), namely scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework and in the Brokering WG as well as participated in the yearly plenary sessions of the network. Moreover, the project participants have represented the project outputs in RDA plenaries and other sessions.

This chapter will introduce the alignment activities of the project partners within RDA Working Groups, where they have represented the services. Overall these activities have allowed the co-design of services, ensuring the further alignment of the products. Information on the participation of the partners to the plenary sessions can be found from the table in Annex 1., summarising the actions.

4.5.1 RDA Working Groups

This chapter outlines some of the working groups within RDA where FAIRCORE4EOSC partners have been active. The working groups have served as great platforms to share knowledge and to further develop the services. One of the groups, FAIR Mappings, was established by FAIRCORE4EOSC jointly with sister project, FAIR-IMPACT, demonstrating the tangible benefits that alignment can bring for projects. More on these groups below.

4.5.1.1 Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework

The Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) working group was endorsed in June 2023, following on from work started by the Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data interest group and is currently in the phase of producing deliverables, focusing primarily on a common Data Model and a format and mechanism for bulk exchange of Scientific Knowledge Graph data.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project (FC4E) has been represented in this working group by participants from WP3 and colleagues from some of the Case Studies and Demonstrators - as SKGs form the basis of many of the service outputs from this work package. The WG has been focused towards developing a foundational framework to enable diverse SKGs to interoperate more seamlessly, ensuring improved data sharing, reusability, and integration across scientific domains.

The outputs of this WG have great relevance to the work performed in FC4E, contributing to the design and development of several of the WP3 services that are focused on mass-exchange of data. The data model produced by the WG lowers barriers to adoption of FC4E services by providing a common metadata format, also enabling leverage of services beyond WP3, such as the Metadata Schema Crosswalk Registry and the Data Type Registry.

Alignment of diverse data sources towards a common method of interoperability and data exchange has great synergy with the goals of FC4E, and enhances the support for all the pillars of the FAIR Principles, with a specific focus on making data provided by FC4E services Accessible and Interoperable.

In the PIDGraph services, collaborative work undertaken in the WG meetings towards the design of the snapshot format was both shaped by existing development undertaken towards producing the PIDGraph Data Dumps, allowing feedback from early iterations and the Beta Release Milestone to be fed into the technical work around designing the snapshot format, and also provided valuable insight from potential adopters beyond the FC4E project as to how they would potentially work with the data outputs from the PIDGraph,

ensuring that the utility, impact, and interoperability of the developed PIDGraph services extended beyond the confines of the project and into the wider scientific community.

Additionally, the common data format produced by the WG has fed into future development plans for the PIDGraph services beyond the end of the FC4E project, enabling the work done during the project to have a continued benefit for both project partners and for external communities.

4.5.1.2 FAIR Mappings

The FAIR Mapping working group was endorsed in February 2025 and will go on until August 2026. The WG has co-chair from both FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT projects and it has been a great extension to the collaboration between the projects as well with the global audience of the RDA. The goals and planned deliverables of the WG are very well aligned with the goals and features of the MSCR service. The WG will emphasize the need for mapping and crosswalk registries, develop mapping representations (content and metadata) and work on shared ontology for mappings. The group has had a good momentum from the beginning with almost 70 members to date with active participation in the bi-weekly meetings.

Even with the project ending, the strong presence of deliverables of the WP4 will continue in the working group and as the outputs of the WG mature there are many opportunities to utilise services provided by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

4.5.1.3 Brokering Working Group

The RDA Brokering Working Group has carried out the bulk of its efforts prior to the start of FAIRCORE4EOSC, and has worked on the broader categorisation and theory of different types of mapping problems. The WG suffered from a combination of retirements from its chairs as well as people changing work topics. Wim Hugo (affiliated with FAIRCORE4EOSC) was one of the only remaining ones left, and invited the FAIRCORE4EOSC project coordinator (Tommi Suominen) to join as a co-chair to wrap things up. The Brokering WG contextualises the work on the MSCR development, and provides the broader theoretical framework for where our work sits. This collaboration would optimally culminate in a scientific publication combining the theoretical outputs of the WG as a contextualisation for the MSCR methodology, but due to limited project resources, this has dropped out in the prioritisation of tasks.

4.6 SWITCH

SWITCH (the Swiss NREN) is running a national aggregation service that relies heavily on RML mappings. Based on initial discussions a Letter of Intent was signed that would allow SWITCH and FAIRCORE4EOSC WP4 to collaborate on management of RML based mappings. The collaboration was based on the experiences and expertise of SWITCH in using the same technologies to solve real world mapping problems in production environments. During the active development and prototyping cycles the coordination and planning of the work was done in weekly meetings between the FAIRCORE4EOSC MSCR dev team (CSC) and SWITCH.

Collaboration with SWITCH has provided a clear and concrete case to reflect and develop the RDF related functionality of the MSCR. All in all, the collaboration worked as a great catalyst to the RML generation feature of the MSCR. The results of our work were also presented in the EuroCRIS Paris event in November 2024 and as part of the RML group meeting in Ghent in December 2024.

Inspired by the success of the first prototypes, a decision was made to start a collaborative implementation of a new version of the RML generator that would be easier to use also outside of the MSCR. A working prototype with support for simple mappings was completed in March 2025. For more details on the implementation and alignment of technical activities, see Deliverable 4.1 (to be published 05/2025).

4.7 GWDG Lol PIDinst proposal

Persistent identifiers for instruments is an initiative that originated in the RDA working group ‘Persistent Identification of Instruments WG’. After the conclusion of the recommendation, the group continued to work under the name PIDINST to advance the topic. One of the aims of the work is to establish a service landscape for the registration of instruments. For this reason, an application to the DFG (German Research Funder) was submitted, unfortunately without success. The support from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project should be provided for integration with FAIRCORE4EOSC services, such as the Data Type Registry (DTR).

Although the proposal to DFG was not successful, the PIDINST community continued their work. The schema to describe an instrument, derived by the PIDINST community, was registered in the DTR of FAIRCORE4EOSC. FAIRCORE4EOSC GWDG partner implemented the schema in a dedicated service instance B2Inst, which is derived from the [B2Share](#) software stack. Final steps have to be done to make B2Inst an official EUDAT service.

The sensor identification in the Sensor Management System (SMS) for the Helmholtz research field Earth & Environment uses the B2Inst service as a backend for creating Persistent Identifiers.

With the collaboration the results of the PIDINST community can reach higher visibility. The possible integration with EOSC core service supports a long-term perspective which is required for service providing persistent information.

5 Lessons learned

This chapter outlines the main lessons learned from the alignment activities introduced in previous chapters.

Major changes in EOSC implementation

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project has encountered issues to integrate the developed services into EOSC due to the major changes in the EOSC implementation strategy during the lifetime of FAIRCORE4EOSC as described in the previous chapters.

These challenges have caused the FAIRCORE4EOSC to adjust its original plans over the course of the project to ensure the sustainability of the project outputs in the short and medium term. As EOSC has currently no additional way of endorsing the services developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC as officially EOSC-related besides the potential EOSC Node integration by other actors than the project, we cannot claim that all the project outputs will be affiliated with the EOSC after the project with absolute certainty.

In general, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project has planned to produce services, addressing gaps in FAIR according to the SRIA v1.0. **The services that the project has developed are now produced and launched, and carry added value in advancing FAIR even if they would not be EOSC services in future by definition.** Thus, the main contribution of the project to the future of the EOSC partnership is indeed the services that have been developed in the course of the project. The project has spent a lot of time and effort in adapting to the new operational environment and crafting for each service separately an individual sustainability and exploitation plan that will be carried outside the project realm. The post-project exploitation and sustainability plans are introduced in the deliverable D7.3 *Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities* where you can read more detailed plans on the exploitation of the services and future EOSC contribution.

- Adapting to critical changes in the project’s operational environment complicates sustainability planning radically and consumes a lot of time and effort, which is not economical from the project’s resourcing point of view.
- The lack of clear statements with respect to the sustainability of the project services hampered the engagement with and the uptake of the services by the strategic communities presented in chapter four.
- In the future, the EC should refrain from changing the policy directions drastically from what was described in the call texts. Any major changes to what the EC seeks to achieve through INFRAEOSC or other calls should be articulated and negotiated at the latest in the Grant Agreement Preparation phase to ensure a realistic project plan and impact.
- Going forwards, the EC should
 - Clarify the process and criteria to establish new Federating Capabilities within the EOSC Federation.
 - Develop a sustainable funding model to maintain and operate a Federating Capability beyond the development through the HE WP funding calls.

EOSC partnership

During the course of the project, FAIRCORE4EOSC partners have been active on many frontiers sharing their expertise on PIDs, metadata, interoperability, FAIR and much more (EOSC-A TFs, OAs, HE WGs) for the benefit of the partnership and have contributed to the EOSC implementation at large, including the EOSC Federation Handbook. The project has also contributed to and attended all the major EOSC events (EOSC Symposia, Winter Schools and Coordination meetings), making FAIRCORE4EOSC a proactive and well-connected community member.

All these alignment activities with the EOSC Partnership have demonstrated that it is beneficial to maintain cooperation and engagement like this, especially because the landscape has changed quickly. The EOSC initiative has undergone many changes during the project life cycle, challenging the original plans for FAIRCORE4EOSC service uptake. If the project would not have engaged in the alignment activities outlined in this report, the project would have had much more trouble trying to adapt to the changed circumstances. This would have also risked the ability of the project to get its voice heard.

Despite the partners representing mainly their own home organisations in the EOSC-A TFs and OAs, they have been used as avenues to receive feedback on the services developed by the project.

- Strategic alignment with the EOSC Partnership via the TFs, OAs and Coordination meetings has been crucial for keeping up with the EOSC developments and understanding their implications on the project as well as establishing connections with the EOSC community members.
- Participation in the HE C&E WG has ensured a broader outreach for the communication while the Impact WG has provided a learning experience for the project to think about Key Exploitable Results and aspects for sustaining services beyond the project life-cycle, building on the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology introduced by Ilaria Nardello, EOSC-A.

INFRAEOSC projects

It is important to keep in mind that collaboration on concrete technical development work for two projects that each are developing their own new technologies is not easy to materialise. This is due to both needing to comply with their own grant agreements and the work defined therein. But also as projects with tight timelines will likely have the results coming very late in the project lifetime, the time window for building collaboration

based on those is very short. Early communication about expected final outputs may on one hand avoid duplication of efforts, but on the other may also raise expectations early. Here, it is helpful to define a feasible timeline of joint actions at an early stage and to ensure that there are regular contacts to manage expectations.

- Defining a feasible timeline of joint actions at an early stage and plan for regular contacts to manage expectations is a good strategy to pursue alignment between projects that are in the making.
- ‘Formalising’ collaborative relationships through Memorandums of Understanding or Letters of Intent with other projects with whom collaboration was not initially foreseen is time consuming. We recommend that projects collaborate in mutual understanding without formal documents where feasible.

Other communities

The project has concluded that it is very useful to maintain a close connection between service developers and case study implementation teams to ensure a smooth feedback loop. In FAIRCORE4EOSC the case studies provided an opportunity for alignment with the scientific communities that they represented. Simultaneously, the project has also learned that it is important to prioritise and find a good balance between the requirements list and what is feasible and practical to implement during one project.

Engagement and alignment with external communities was hindered to a certain extent by the lack of clear statements with respect to the sustainability of the project services. FAIRCORE4EOSC was very challenged by this point, as the plans regarding sustainability were in limbo for much of the project, due to the changes in the operational EOSC environment.

It is useful to align the work on interoperability with global communities to ensure alignment already at an early stage. Usability of data outputs is also enhanced by common data formats and interchange methods. For example, within the RDA community, mappings serve as a cross-cutting theme, allowing collaboration between different working groups to ensure knowledge sharing and alignment of activities.

6 Conclusions

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project has aligned with different projects and communities during the project life-cycle to create synergies and to ensure that the services cater for actual user needs within and beyond EOSC. Moreover, by being an active EOSC community member and liaising with the EOSC partnership, FAIRCORE4EOSC has striven for delivering services that are aligned with the broader objectives of the EOSC vision, albeit not officially endorsed by or labelled as EOSC. By aligning with the EOSC partnership and contributing to its goals, the project has ensured that the service development of the project influences the future evolution of EOSC.

The strategic alignment carried out throughout the project has confirmed that it is of utmost importance that the project is able to exchange views and discuss with other relevant initiatives to co-develop services and try to align with the overall goals of EOSC.

The alignment does not happen without challenges, which the project has encountered e.g. with contributions to the EOSC federation as the new developments within EOSC have created uncertainties, but carefully thought out risk planning can help forecast some key issues.

Finally, the ultimate motivation for strategic alignment is that we want the work we carry out to have a positive impact. These activities act as an impact multiplier for technical service development work. By carrying out

these alignment activities successfully, through impact generation, we create for the work itself meaning and motivation for the staff to carry it out. It is not just that we have invested around 85 person years of labour effort into this, and gotten paid salaries for that, but the fulfilment of having used that huge amount of human life responsibly for a meaningful purpose.

Appendix A: FAIRCORE4EOSC representation in RDA plenaries and other events

Event	Working group / other activity	FAIRCORE4EOSC contribution (+ alignment with other projects)
<i>RDA P20 Gothenburg</i>	Research Software workshop	FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC co-hosted the "Research Software Workshop: Guidelines and Metrics for Metadata Curation" to gather current guidelines for research software metadata, assess gaps based on EOSC's SIRS report, review and expand the CodeMeta vocabulary for improved interoperability, and discuss mechanisms to enhance metadata quality for research software.
	Brokering Framework Working Group	The outputs generated by the Brokering framework Working Group were reviewed with the community with a view to concluding its operations and transferring its work in progress to the proposed WG FAIR Mappings.
<i>RDA P21 Salzburg</i>	FAIR Mappings Working Group	A BoF session "Let's talk about FAIR mappings! Towards common practices for sharing mappings and crosswalks" Jointly with FAIR-IMPACT
<i>RDA VP22</i>	FAIR Mappings WG	BoF - Let's keep talking about mappings !! - a BoF session organised by the proposed FAIR Mappings WG and co-chaired from FAIRCORE4EOSC WP4 and FAIRIMPACT
<i>RDA P23</i>	FAIR Mappings WG	BoF Session "FAIR Mappings - Let's start working" organized and presented by FAIRCORE4EOSC WP4 and FAIR-

		Impact. In collaboration with the FAIR-Impact project. One presenter from WP4.
RDA VP24	FAIR Mappings WG	WG Session “FAIR Mappings WG – Use case highlights and the initial taxonomy for mappings”. In collaboration with the FAIR-Impact project. One presenter from WP4.
	SKG-IF Working Group	WG Session “Making the point on interoperability across Scientific Knowledge Graphs – Debriefing from the SKG-IF WG”: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presenters from WP3 ● Relevance of work done in FC4E towards wider RDA WG goals